

Phase Separation in Mixed Compositions Containing Crystallizable Copoly(Urethane-Imide) and Crystallizable Polyimide

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A number of samples of copoly(urethane-imide)s **CPUI (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R)(BAPB)_n** ($n=1,2,3,5$) was synthesized based on poly(diethylene glycol) adipate ($M_n=2500$) (**2500**) terminated with 2,4-toluylenediisocyanate (**TDI**), bis(3',4-dicarboxyphenoxy)benzene (dianhydride **R**) and 1,4-bis(4'-aminophenoxy)biphenyl (diamine **BAPB**). **CPUI** are distinguished by the content of aromatic blocks in the polymer from 37 to 65% (mass). The synthesized samples were characterized by TGA, DSC and MTA methods. **CPUI** were used to prepare mixed compositions with polyimide (**R-BAPB**). These compositions contained 10% (mass) and 90% (mass) polyimide, respectively. The compositions were investigated using the DSC method. The influence of increase of the relative content of imide units on the T_g and T_m values of copolymers and mixed compositions are traced. This influence is due to the separation and interaction of aromatic (imide) and aliphatic (polyester) phases contained in the investigated polymer systems.

Keywords: copoly(urethane-imide), polyimide, polymer mixture, thermoplastic, thermoelastoplast, TGA, DSC, MTA, melt rheology, phase separation, rubber-like elasticity.

INTRODUCTION

Polyimides are of industrial importance. Coatings, films, plastics, foams have been developed on their basis. These materials are capable of operation in extreme conditions ^[1]. Important products of polyimide modification are poly(amide-imide)s ^[2], multiblock (segment) copoly(ether-imide)s ^[3] and copoly(urethane-imide)s ^[4-10]. Copoly(urethane-imide)s form a subclass of heat-resistant polymers and are important as heat-resistant elastomers ^[11] and as pervaporation membranes for separation of aromatic and aliphatic hydrocarbon mixtures ^[12].

Methods of synthesis of copoly(urethane-imide)s (**CPUI**) are collected in ^[11]. Each polymer repeating unit contains a hard block of aromatic imide terminated by urethane groups and a soft block of aliphatic polyester. Due to the thermodynamic incompatibility of hard aromatic and soft aliphatic blocks, microphase separation takes place in the volume of polymers. In this case, each phase is characterized by its inherent T_g . At the same time, T_m presence or absence is determined by the possibility of phase crystallization. The separation and interaction of phases in PUI systems determine the changes in T_g and T_m values by variation of the chemical structure and composition of these systems.

Due to phase separation, multiblock(segment) copoly(urethane-imide)s acquire the properties of elastomers. Glass transition temperatures (T_g) are in the negative temperature range on the Celsius scale, dynamic mechanical analysis curves are characterized by areas (plateaus) of rubber-like elasticity, the relative tensile elongations of samples are measured in hundreds of percent [13].

Earlier in our research group, chemical modification of polyimides was performed using polyesters/polyethers terminated with 2,4-toluylenediisocyanate: polypropylene glycol ($M_n=2300$), poly(ethylene adipate) ($M_n=2700$) and poly(1,6-hexanediol/neopentylglycol-cher-adipic acid ($M_n=900$) [14-20]. The list of initial polyesters/polyethers is extended in the present work: poly(diethylene glycol)adipate diol ($M_n=2500$) was used as a modifying agent. It is characterized by the increased content of carboxylate groups. Modification of thermoplastic polyimides with polyurethanes (based on polyesters/polyethers) facilitates the processing conditions of the obtained polymers in comparison with the initial ones. Thus, the transition from thermoplastic polyimides to thermoplastic elastomers of increased heat resistance and strength is carried out.

Thermoplastic elastomers, which can be processed by injection molding, are designated as thermoelastoplasts. Chemistry and technology of thermoelastoplasts (thermoplastic elastomers) is the fastest growing area of the polymer industry. Therefore, the reverse transition from copoly(urethane-imide) elastomers to polyimide thermoplastics is of great theoretical and practical interest. The design of polymer systems should be developed in the direction of strengthening (the increase of the length or molecular weight) of hard aromatic blocks in the case of multiblock (segmented) copoly(urethane-imide)s and in the direction of increase of the mass fraction of aromatic blocks in the case of statistical copoly(urethane-imide)s. Besides, by means of the increase of polyimide mass fraction in mixed compositions with copoly(urethane-imide)s.

The objectives of this work include:

- the synthesis of a new multiblock copoly(urethane-imide) (R-TDI2500TDI-R) (BAPB) based on poly(diethylene glycol) adipate (2500), 2,4-toluene diisocyanate (TDI), dianhydride R and diamine BAPB,
- synthesis of random copolymers (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R) (BAPB)_n (n = 2, 3, 5), characterized by a high content of aromatic blocks,
- preparation of mixtures of synthesized copoly(urethane-imide)s with polyimide R-BAPB in varying proportions,
- and the study of heat resistance and mechanical properties of synthesized polymer systems.

These tasks correspond to the main goal of the work - to reveal common factors of change in the T_g and T_m values in the synthesized polymer systems due to the separation and interaction of aromatic (imide) and aliphatic (polyester) microphases.

Experimental part

Starting reagents

The following starting materials were used for the preparation of polymers: dianhydride 1,3-bis(3',4-dicarboxyphenoxy)benzene (dianhydride **R**), T_m 163-165°C (LLC "Techhimprom", Yaroslavl, Russia); diamine 1,4-bis(4'-aminophenoxy)biphenyl (diamine **BAPB**), T_m 194-196°C (VWR International,

USA); poly(diethylene glycol)adipate diol (polyester **2500**) $M_n=2500$ (Aldrich); 2,4-toluylenediisocyanate (**TDI**) (Aldrich); phthalic Anhydride (**Pht**), T_m 131 °C (Aldrich).

Test methods

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of the obtained film samples was carried out at TG 209 F1 (NETZSCH, Germany) in the temperature range 30-800°C at a heating rate of 10 °/min in an argon atmosphere. The weight of the samples was 2-3 mg. As a result of the experiment, temperatures of 5 and 10% mass loss (T_5 , T_{10}), heat resistance indices, and residual mass at 800°C were determined.

The glass transition (T_g), melting (T_m) and crystallization (T_{cr}) temperatures, as well as the enthalpy of melting and crystallization (ΔH) of the samples were determined by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) on the DSC 204 F1 instrument (NETZSCH, Germany) at a temperature rise rate of 10 °/min in the range from -20 to +380°C in an argon atmosphere. The weight of the samples was 4-5 mg, T_g was determined by the results of the second scan.

Temperature dependences of dynamic elastic modulus (E'), loss modulus (E'') and mechanical loss tangent ($\text{tg } \delta$) of film samples of multiblock copolymers and composites were obtained by dynamic mechanical analysis (DMA) at DMA 242 C (NETZSCH, Germany). Measurements were carried out at a frequency of 1 Hz, the amplitude of deformation of the films was 0.1%, the rate of temperature rise 5°C / min. T_g of the film samples was determined by the temperature of the maxima and inflections of the temperature dependences ($\text{tg } \delta$).

Deformation-strength properties were determined using INSTRON 5943 universal breaking machine. The tensile speed was 5 mm/min. The base length of the film samples was 20 mm, the width was 2 mm.

The polymer synthesis

CPUI of general formula were chosen as the object of research in the work:

where $n=1,2,3,5$ were selected.

CPUI synthesis was carried out according to the methods worked out in [15, 17] according to the scheme including intermediate formation of a macromonomer with terminal anhydride groups. Below is the scheme for the case of CPUI ($n=1$):

Synthesis of copoly(urethane-imide) (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R) (BAPB) with thermal imidization of the prepolymer in solution in N-methyl-2-pyrrolidone (N-MP). Polyester 2500 was fused with of 2,4-toluylenediisocyanate (TDI) taken in two-fold molar excess in a three-necked thermostating flask equipped with a stirrer and a input-output tube for argon. The dianhydride R was added in stoichiometric amount in the derived melt of polyester 2500 terminated by 2,4-toluylenediisocyanate (the intermediate TDI-2500-TDI (**1**)). It was necessary for the interaction with the terminal isocyanate groups of the product (**1**), to obtain the macromonomer (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R) (**2**) with terminal anhydride groups. Then the melt of the flask were heated to complete the release of carbon dioxide (a byproduct of the reaction of isocyanates with cyclic anhydrides). N-MP was poured in the flask after the completion of gas formation. Into derived solution of macromonomer (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R) (**2**) at room temperature diamine (BAPB) was introduced in stoichiometric amounts necessary for polyacylation of diamine by the terminal anhydride groups of the macromonomer (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R) (**2**). The resulted solution of polyamidoacid prepolymer (**3**) was subjected to thermal imidization in the same solution (N-MP). Imidization water was taken in the form of azeotrope with toluene, using a Dean-Stark nozzle. Films were obtained from the CPUI solution upon completion of imidization.

IR, ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectroscopy data confirm the stated structure of copoly(urethane imide)s (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R)(BAPB).

The infrared spectrum (FTIR), ν/cm^{-1} : 3345, 3067, 2935, 2866, 1776, 1714, 1593, 1533, 1506, 1488, 1473, 1442, 1365, 1307, 1224, 1166, 1120, 972, 875, 827, 744

NMR spectrum ¹H (DMSO-d₆, δ , m.d.): 9.85, 9.61, 9.07, 8.85, 7.97, 7.70, 7.51, 7.44, 7.29, 7.17, 7.08, 4.11, 3.59, 2.30, 2.11, 2.02, 1.53

NMR spectrum ¹³C (DMSO-d₆, δ , m.d.): 173.1, 166.5, 162.5, 157.0, 134.7, 131.3, 129.5, 128.7, 126.3, 124.1, 119.9, 119.1, 116.8, 113.0, 112.3, 68.7, 63.4, 33.5, 24.3

*In the cases of SPUI synthesis (n = 2,3,5) at the stage of substitution of terminal isocyanate groups of the intermediate product TDI-2500-TDI (**1**) with anhydride groups, dianhydride R was added to the reaction mixture in an amount exceeding the molar stoichiometric ratio of the reacting substances (Table 1). As a result, the products formed during acylation of the diamine BAPB with the molecules of macromonomer (R-TDI-Alt-TDI-R) (**2**) and dianhydride R, which are present in the reaction solution, are among the random copolymers.*

The values of the characteristic viscosity of the synthesized CPUI ranged from 0.40 to 0.52 dl/g.

Preparation of samples of prepolymer (PAA) of polyimide R-BAPB was carried out in solution in N-MP according to the known technique [3]. The molar ratio of the starting substances was R: Pht: BAPB= 0.95: 0.10: 1.0.

Preparation of mixed compositions

Preparation of mixed compositions was carried out by mixing of obtained CPUI solution with polyamidoacid solutions of R-BAPB in N-MP. Imidization of prepolymers and processing of polyimides were carried out according to above-described methods: the PAA and CPUI solution was cast on hydrophobized glass

substrates, dried at 80 °C and after curing, the film was heated by a stepwise mode of 100, 200, 300°C. The thickness of the resulting film coatings was 80-100 microns.

Table 1. Molar ratios of initial substances in the preparation of CPUI

CPUI	TDI2500TDI	BAPB	R	(% mass)
n=1	1.0	1.0	2.0	37
n=2	1.0	2.0	3.0	47
n=3	1.0	3.0	4.0	55
n=5	1.0	5.0	6.0	65

Results and discussion

CPUI with an increased content of hard blocks are selected as the objects of research in the present work. Earlier the problem of increasing the proportion of aromatic blocks in multiblock (segmented) CPUI was solved in our work [17,20]. It was achieved by introducing the starting monomers into the reaction systems in predetermined sequences and stoichiometric molar ratios. In this case, macromonomers with reaction groups (isocyanate, anhydride, amine) were obtained, which were combined in the selected sequences. In the present work we turned to statistical poly(urethane-imide) block copolymers. It makes it possible to significantly simplify the procedure of obtaining of CPUI with a higher content of aromatic blocks. In this case the synthesis scheme includes the synthesis of macromonomer with terminal anhydride groups, which in a mixture of a given composition with dianhydride monomer (Table 1) enters into the reaction of joint polycondensation with diamine monomer. The products obtained are statistical copolymers of urethane-imide with imide.

Fig.1. Study of films (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R) (BAPB) (n=1): a-TGA curves, b-DSC curves, c-DMA curves.

On the fig.1, the curves of TGA, DSC and DMA of samples of multiblock copoly(urethane-imide) (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R)(BAPB) ($n=1$), which in a number of studied polymers has the lowest content of imide blocks, are given.

According to the TGA (fig.1a) the studied sample has a high temperature resistance: index T_5 (temperature corresponding to 5% mass loss) lies in the range of 356°C-358°C. According to DSC data (fig.1b) the glass transition is observed at -32.2°C. The sample has two crystalline phases. The observed endotherm at 49°C ($\Delta H = 4.6$ J/g) should be attributed to the melting of the aliphatic polyester phase. The endotherm at 288.7°C ($\Delta H = 1.3$ J/g) is attributed to the melting of the aromatic (imide) phase. The peak on the DSC curve in the region of 216°C-218°C indicates the crystallization of aromatic (imide) segments during heating (T_{cr}), amorphization of polymers takes place at the second scan. There is a developed plateau of rubber-like elasticity on the temperature dependence curves E' and E'' (fig.1c). The formation of the extrema on the temperature dependence of $\tan \delta$ (fig.1c) indicates the glass transition temperature of the aliphatic phase (-16°C) and detects a wide peak responsible for the temperature region of partial compatibility of the aliphatic and aromatic phases (51°C), and indicates the glass transition of the aromatic phase (85°C). The transition of the sample to a viscous state below 120°C registered by the DMA method makes it possible to strengthen the structural organization (orientation) of the aromatic copolymer blocks during heating. The last circumstance is reflected in the DSC curves.

The following are the results of the study of the sample of statistical CPUI and (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R)(BAPB)₅ ($n=5$) with the highest content of imide blocks (fig.2) by TGA, DSC and DMA methods.

The sample (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R)(BAPB)₅ ($n=5$) with a high content of imide blocks is characterized by a relatively high temperature resistance: the index value of T_5 increases to 375 °C (fig.2a). This sample is characterized (fig.2b) by two T_g (-19.3 °C and 158.5°C) relating, respectively, to the devitrification of aliphatic and aromatic blocks, but one T_m (304.5°C) relating to the melting of aromatic blocks. Crystallization of the aliphatic (soft) phase is not detected by DSC. The melting endotherm is visible on the curve of the second scan, and this indicates incomplete amorphization of the sample as a result of melting. Most likely, the crystallization of soft blocks is suppressed with an increase of the content of hard blocks in the CPUI. DMA method on a sample with a high content of imide blocks ($n=5$) (fig.2b) more clearly detects two glass transition of thermodynamically incompatible blocks (-27,4 °C and 160,2 °C) and the

temperature range of their partial compatibility (65°C) than in the case of a sample with a low content of these blocks (fig.1c).

Fig.2. Study of films (R-TDI2500TDI-R) (BAPB)₅ (n=5): a-curves TGA, b-DSC, c-DMA.

Table 2. The study of the CPUI by methods of DSC and TGA

CPUI	DSC(first scan)				DSC (second scan)			Residual weight , %(800°C)	T ₅ , °C
	T _m , °C	ΔH, J/g	T _{crL} , °C	ΔH, J/g	T _m , °C	ΔH, J/g	T _g , °C		
n=1	52.8 289	9 1.3	218, 3	0,4			-30.9	21.8	358
n=2	46.1 291.2	7.6; 7.3					-33.7 142	26	350
n=3	64.7 294.8	3.2; 18.7			304.8	1.7	-37 152.6	34	360
n=5	57.5 300.7	4.2; 25.8			308.4 309	3 2.3	-40.8 163.7	38.9	368

The general view of the phase transitions observed in the studied polymers is given by the data in table. 2, which summarizes the results of studies of synthesized SPUI by DSC and TGA methods.

Glass transitions, manifested in the second scan in studies by DSC, refer to the devitrification of aliphatic polyester blocks (they are located in the minus temperature region) and imide blocks (they are located in the plus temperature region). The gaps between the T_g values corresponding to the softening of polyester (flexible) and imide (hard) blocks grow as the content of aromatic (imide) blocks in copolymers increases. This circumstance indicates the thermodynamic incompatibility of these blocks. The melting heats of the imide (hard) phase determined by the first DSC scan also grow with the increase of content of imide blocks in the copolymers. The results of the second DSC scan show that CPUI with a high content of hard blocks ($n= 3,5$) are capable of recrystallization after melting.

As follows from the TGA data (table 2), the studied CPUI have a high thermo-oxidative stability: the values of the temperature resistance indices τ_5 lie above 350°C. The residual mass (coke residue) increases to 38% with an increase of the mass content of imide blocks in the CPUI.

The stress-strain characteristics of the studied CPUI depend on the ratio of aromatic (hard) and aliphatic (soft) blocks contained in their structure (table.3).

Table 3. Strain-stress properties of CPUI films

CPUI	E, MPa	σ_b , MPa	ϵ_p , %
n=1	12,0	2,0	966,0
n=2	134,0	7,0	173,0
n=3	439,0	15,0	156,0
n=5	929,0	34,0	72,0

Samples are presented in order of increase of weight fraction of aromatic blocks in them in table 3. It should be noted a sharp increase in the elastic modulus of films: about two orders of magnitude. In accordance with the changes in the module, the tendency to the increase of tensile strength (from 2 MPa to 33 MPa) is observed. There is a sharp drop in elongation values at break (from 960% to 70%).

Fig. 3 illustrates the change in the deformation mechanism of samples with an increase of the content of imide blocks in the CPUI.

Fig.3. Tensile curves of CPUI film samples $(R-TDI2500TDI-R)(BAPB)$ ($n=1$), $(R-TDI2500TDI-R)(BAPB)_2$ ($n=2$), $(R-TDI2500TDI-R)(BAPB)_3$ ($n=3$), $(R-TDI2500TDI-R)(BAPB)_5$ ($n=5$).

Figure 3 shows that an increase in the proportion of aromatic blocks in the copolymers leads to a sharp change in the nature of the tensile curves. The course of the tensile curve of the sample (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R) (BAPB) ($n=1$) is typical for deformation of elastomers. This sample has a high deformation before rupture and a low modulus of tension. When the proportion of imide blocks in the CPUI increases with a simultaneous increase in the modulus of elasticity, the deformation before rupture decreases. Starting with the sample ((P-TDI2500TDI-R) (BAPB) 3 ($n = 3$), a peak of plasticity appears, which is the characteristic of thermoplastic polymers. In the case of the sample (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R)(BAPB)5 ($n=5$), such a peak becomes clearer, which is associated with the formation of the neck when the sample is tested. Thus, we can go from elastomers to thermoplastics and back from thermoplastics to elastomers by changing the content of imide blocks in the studied CPUI.

The design of polymer systems with a maximum content of imide blocks is possible in the case of mixed compositions containing both copoly(urethane-imide)s and polyimides. Such non-segregating in a common solution (in an amide solvent) mixtures can be prepared if the aromatic blocks of the copoly(urethane-imide) and the repeating unit of the polyimide are identical in chemical structure. In the present work, films that did not undergo crack due to the separation of the components of the mixture were prepared on the basis of the synthesized CPUI and polyimide R-BAPB. The compositions were prepared in two versions: with a polyimide content of 10% (wt) and 90% (wt), respectively. All mixed compositions were investigated using the DSC method.

A typical picture of differences in the properties of compositions depending on the content of polyimide in them is shown as an example in Fig.4 for the case (R-TDI-2500-TDI-R)(BAPB)₃ ($n=3$).

Fig.4. DSC curves of samples: a - (R-TDI2500TDI-R)(BAPB)₃ ($n=3$), b - a mixture of 90%(mass) (R-TDI2500TDI-R)(BAPB)₃ and 10%(mass) (R-BAPB), c - the mixture: 10% (mass) (R-TDI2500TDI-R)(BAPB)₃ and 90% (mass)(R-BAPB), d - (R-BAPB)

As can be seen from fig.4, the introduction into the polymer system of polyimide in an amount of 10% (mass) does not lead to a significant change in the course of the DSC curves (fig.4, a and b). In the case of 90% polyimide content in the mixture, the crystallization exotherm appears on the curve of the first scan (fig.4c), the melting heat of the composition ($\Delta H = 27 \text{ J/g}$) is significantly higher than the melting heat of the original polyimide ($\Delta H = 17 \text{ J/g}$) (fig.4d). The noted circumstance suggests a cocrystallization of imide blocks belonging to polyimides and CPUI, respectively. At the first scanning of the sample containing 10% (mass) of polyimide, two glass transitions (at $-39,4^\circ\text{C}$ and $150,8^\circ\text{C}$) are observed (fig.4b); at 90% content of polyimide in the sample, one transition takes place (at $185,3^\circ\text{C}$) (Fig. 4c). That is, the process of devitrification of imide blocks in the composition is hindered and shifts to high temperature range. Differences in the properties of mixed compositions depending on the structure of the initial CPUI are traced according to the data in the table. 4, which presents the results of studies of mixed compositions by DSC and TGA. The samples are arranged as the mass fraction of imide blocks increases in the structure of the CPUI.

Table 5. Investigation of mixed compositions by DSC and TGA methods

CPUI	DSC(first scan)			DSC (second scan)			Residual weight , %(800°C)	$T_5, ^\circ\text{C}$
	$T_m, ^\circ\text{C}$	$\Delta H, \text{J/g}$	$T_{cr}, ^\circ\text{C} / \Delta H, \text{J/g}$	DCK $T_g, ^\circ\text{C}$	$T_m, ^\circ\text{C}$	$\Delta H, \text{J/g}$		
Compositions containing 10%(mass) polyimide								

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n=1	54.7; 292.1; 323.6	5.3; 8.4; 0.5		-34.2; 213.4	301.1	0.4		25.1	348
n=2	51.6; 294.1	9.3; 14.8		-35.3; 145.3	305.1	1.2		30.5	363
n=3	54.9; 297.7	7.4; 21.2		-38.2; 150.2	307	2.3		34.5	354
n=5	73.5; 300.1	6.7; 30.4		-41.5; 165.5	310.4	3.2		40	375
Compositions containing 90% (mass) polyimide									
n=1	317.3	32.1	262.4/ 31.7	182.7	318.4	20.7	282.8/ 18.3	49	385
n=2	63.4; 316.6	8.4; 34.5	259.7/ 28.9	178.6	319.1	5.6		49	374
n=3	57.6; 318.1	8.2; 27.9	276.5/ 24.8	182.8	320.3	1.5		49.3	372
n=5	317.8	30	262.4/ 26.6	190.3	320.3	3,6		3.8	374
Original polyimide (R-BAPB)Pht (for comparison)	318.6	17.2		201.3				56.3	542

According to the table.5, it is possible to make general conclusions about the influence of the compound of the mixed compositions on the characteristics of their heat resistance. Samples of compositions containing 10% (wt) of polyimide, characterized by two T_g , relating to devitrification of polyester soft blocks and hard imide blocks. Samples with 90% polyimide content are characterized by one T_g related to the devitrification of imide blocks, and the T_g values increase as the proportion of aromatic blocks increases in the CPUI. All mixed compositions are characterized by two T_m , i.e. have two crystalline phases. It is reasonable to associate the changes in T_m values observed as the studied systems are loaded with imide cycles, with the interaction of phases. It should be noted that in the case of mixtures with 90% content of polyimide, it is possible to observe recrystallization by rescanning. The mixed systems have a high thermo-oxidative stability, the values of τ_5 lie in the range of 350-385 °C.

Thus, the variation of the relative content of polyester (soft) and imide (hard) blocks in CPUi and their compositions with polyimide is an efficient mean of influence on the characteristics of microphases (T_g and T_m) formed in the polymer systems under consideration, and as a consequence of phase separation, on the mechanical properties and thermal stability of polymers.

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**STEPI BOOK
Volume 11**

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Deborah Jones & Marc J. Abadie**

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PREFACE TO VOLUME 11

Performance Polymers

Volume 11

Montpellier 12 Février 2020

Les 11^{ème} Conférences sur les Polyimides & Polymères Haute Performance a.k.a. STEPI 11 se sont déroulées à Montpellier les 2-5 Juin 2019, Faculté des Sciences de l'Université de Montpellier.

Ces conférences se déroulent toujours dans un cadre jovial, amical et constructif d'un point de vue scientifique, permettant aux nouveaux venus de s'intégrer rapidement à la famille des STEPIers.

Les participants qui ont bien voulu soumettre un article pour l'édition du Volume 11 sont remerciés. Depuis l'origine nous avons toujours publié les articles des conférences qui sont une trace intangible de l'évolution des polymères hétérocycliques au cours de ces trente dernières années.

Les 12^{ème} Conférences sur les Polyimides se tiendront, toujours à Montpellier, Juin 5-8 2022. Elles seront les dernières organisées par nous à Montpellier. Nous souhaiterions, pour que perdure l'esprit STEPI, que ces Conférences se tiennent alternativement dans d'autres villes, en France ou dans d'autres pays. J'espère que nombreux seront intéressés à porter le projet de ces Conférences.

En vous remerciant pour votre implication et votre confiance,

Marc J.M. Abadie, Prof Emeritus

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